

Uncertainty-Identity Theory: A Theoretical Review

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Uncertainty prevails around the world in many aspects, which can lead to an individual questioning their identity and unforeseen future. Uncertainty-Identity Theory, proposed by Michael Hogg, states that to reduce uncertainty, people identify with groups (Hogg, 2007). The theory has rendered its versatile applications in the span of more than two decades, and hence it is crucial to map the findings in order to gauge its practical and theoretical implications and seek the gaps where it could be further utilized as a theoretical framework. This theoretical review has included 846 studies from various databases, and after thorough screening, 25 studies were found to be eligible to be included. Findings of this review are categorized into themes, and future implications have been discussed in detail.

Keywords: Uncertainty-identity theory, social identity, extremism and radical groups, leadership

Uncertainty-Identity Theory, developed by Hogg, is relevant in understanding the present day scenario where uncertainty lies in the financial, personal, and health realms of an individual's life and how identifying with a particular group can facilitate them in reducing uncertainty. Hence, this theory explains the construct of social identity in a much more pertinent manner and signifies its relevance in the contemporary era. It has been more than two decades since the concept of uncertainty-identity was conceptualized as a theory by Michael Hogg in 2007. Since then, numerous empirical studies have been conducted that have built their conceptual framework around Uncertainty-Identity theory and acknowledged its contribution. Hence, a theoretical review becomes important. The essence of uncertainty-identity theory is that group identification through the process of self-categorization is an effective way of reducing self-uncertainty (Desai & Hogg, 2024).

According to Hogg, the identity of self can be construed at a collective level as well, and not just on the individual level (Czepluch et al., 2025). He further states that once group members internalize being part of a group, the distinctiveness between self and group begins to fade (Li et al., 2024). Also, even if an individual shares different social identities, which identity becomes salient depends on the context, as per Hogg (Chao, 2025).

Historical Background of Uncertainty-Identity Theory

When the historical background of Uncertainty-Identity Theory is considered, the construct of social identity plays a pivotal role. According to Tajfel, people identify with a group to achieve the

emotional significance that comes with being part of that particular group. However, these memberships can later result in intergroup conflicts (Tajfel, 1972; as cited in Hogg, 2007). Later, Turner identified self-enhancement as the key motivator for joining the groups that had positive distinctiveness (Turner, 1975; as cited in Hogg, 2007). Social categorization is another factor that motivates individuals to identify strongly with in groups by minimizing differences within and exaggerating them between outgroups, thus emphasizing the role of Self Categorization Theory, developed by Turner and colleagues (Trepte et al., 2017). This theory has focused on how people join groups with high prototypicality and clearly stated norms, which makes it easier for them to follow rules and identify well with their respective groups. The need for uncertainty reduction can be regarded as one of the factors as to why people categorize themselves strongly in groups, which paves the way towards the development of Uncertainty-Identity Theory.

According to Hogg, groups high in entitativity also help in uncertainty reduction compared to the other groups, as prototypes of those groups are clear to their members (Brown et al., 2021). This can be the reason why, according to Hogg (2007), people belonging to high-entitativity groups show a significant reduction in uncertainty levels, as their norms are clear and act as the anchor in providing certainty to the group members. One such example can be the religious beliefs that can render certainty about self and the world around (Berger & Luckmann, 1967; Griffin, 2012; as cited in Winter & Feixas, 2019). All these prevailing factors have led to the study of Uncertainty-Identity Theory and the shape we see it in today, thus making a thorough review crucial.

Method

“A theoretical literature review brings together all types of literature and aims to contribute a unique theoretical perspective that goes beyond the sum of the individual studies” (Webster & Watson, 2002). To assess the development of Uncertainty-Identity Theory, its contributions, both theoretical and practical, Theoretical Literature Review was found to be an apt method to carry forward with.

To conduct this review on Uncertainty-Identity Theory, premium databases like Taylor and Francis, Scopus, and Springer were included, and studies from 2007 to January 2026 were taken. The enquiry includes the studies beginning from the year 2007, as the theory was published in the same year, and hence the findings of

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various studies were mapped till January, 2026 from 2007. The search string of “Uncertainty-Identity Theory” was used and it generated 846 results (745 from Taylor & Francis, 70 from Scopus ^ 31 from Springer). The search was limited to the custom range of 2007 to 2026, the field was limited to Social Sciences and Psychology, the language of the articles was limited to English, and the type was limited to Open Access only. After screening these articles based on title and abstracts, 31 articles were found to be relevant. To map the relevant findings, the articles were screened again including the full text which led to a total of 25 articles that were included in the present study. Findings from these articles were grouped into two main themes: *Resolving uncertainty by identification with radical and extreme groups* and *Beyond Extremism and Radicalization*, on the basis of prevalence of the issues found in the results from the selected articles.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Studies that involved primary research, both quantitative and qualitative in nature were considered for the current review. Research articles in the English language were included.

Results

As per the results revealed in the literature included in the present review, two themes have been formulated and the studies have been classified as follows:

Resolving Uncertainty by Identification with Radical and Extreme Groups

Radical groups are abundant globally, and it does not take a rational mind to join these as they usually indulge in impulsive behaviors. Uncertainty can lead to identification with the groups that are radicalized and extreme in nature (Hogg, 2013; as cited in Mason et al., 2024) as the individuals can construe their identities better with clear norms and regulations. In a recent study conducted on Sino-Thai individuals during the Nine Emperor God festival, it was revealed that people perform extreme rituals as a part of uncertainty management, which are usually tied to the beliefs of their corresponding groups (Fischer et al., 2024). Thus, religiousness can also act as a way to reduce uncertainty. Even during the pandemic, identifying in solidarity with one's national identity led to alleviated feelings of uncertainty (Maher et al., 2023). Discrimination was also found to be a cause of why people identify more with extremist groups, as facing discriminatory behavior gives way to a lack of personal significance and self-certainty. In such cases, strict norms of a radical group act as a refuge to its members and reduce uncertainty (Shanaah, 2023). In addition to discrimination, psychological distress brought on by frustrated relatedness needs leads to inflexible us-versus-them thinking, which in turn provides identity clarity and certainty, thereby bolstering support for violent extremist views (Briki, 2022). Individuals who felt personally vulnerable, at economic risk, and insecure were found to have raised political trust, as it seemed to have a compensatory psychological function, assisting people in coping with the anxiety that comes with economic instability and uncertainty (deBlok & Haugsgjerd, 2025).

A study conducted in Italy regarding the importance of strong leadership in the uncertain era of COVID-19 pandemic reflected that when identification with fellow nationals was stronger, the wish for a stronger, extremist leader was lower than when the identification with Europeans was concerned (Moscatelli et al.,

2023). The willingness of a group to indulge in social change versus the outgroup that wants to maintain the status quo can bring about a sharp contrast, which can reduce uncertainty by strengthening the social identity (Stollberg et al., 2024). Individuals can perceive uncertainty in the form of immigrants residing in their homeland, as well as consider them a threat to the country's resources. In such scenarios, people vouch for anti-immigration laws and support extremist right-wing political parties to reduce uncertainty to their opportunities and resources (Alves et al., 2024). A recent study has contributed to the literature on radicalism, in which it was found that only agency-oriented people exhibit a preference for joining radical groups under low clarity of self-concept, thus expanding upon Hogg's findings that suggest that individuals join highly radicalized groups when they lack clarity in their self-concept (Choi & Yoon, 2021). However, in a recent study, findings revealed that even though the support for prototypical leaders is higher than the non-prototypical leaders, under highly uncertain conditions, the support for non-prototypical leaders increased (Rast et al., 2012). This particular finding leads one to think the prominent role of uncertainty in life and that in those precarious situations, individuals can take support from the people and resources available on the spot. In some cases, the superordinate identity, or identity on a larger level, like national identity, provides more certainty to the youth with low cognitive flexibility and a quest for significance leads to low identification with extremist groups (Knorr & Kossowska, 2025). This empirical evidence also suggests the importance of easily accessible resources in uncertainty reduction.

Beyond Extremism and Radicalization

The scope of Uncertainty-Identity Theory is not limited to identifying with radical extremist groups in the face of uncertainty. Several other factors come into play that can induce uncertainty in individuals. For example, in a recent meta-analysis, it was found that ostracism can hamper certainty in individuals on an immediate basis, and thus, group belongingness, as per Hogg, becomes necessary to reduce uncertainty (Hales, 2025).

Another major cause could be norms, which, according to Hogg, are derived from the values a group upholds and what the majority of the group members believe in (Hoppe et al., 2025). Expectations of norm violation in a group by ingroup and outgroup members can threaten the social selves of group members, thus creating uncertainty (Ditrich & Sassenberg, 2024). Shifting the focus away from norms, a novel and noteworthy contribution to Uncertainty-Identity Theory comes from the work of Bosman et al. (2024) where the role of social identity in preference for Identity-First Language (IFL) and Person-First Language (PFL) has been discussed in the autistic community, where clients feel high uncertainty and hence prefer IFL, as it considers autism to be the central part of the patient's identity.

The utility of Uncertainty-Identity Theory could be explained in an organizational context as well. Being part of an organization comes with uncertainty in diverse situations, which can affect employees' identification and commitment to the organization. In a recent study, the findings suggested that when employees experienced high uncertainty, the interdependent individuals identified strongly with the organization and displayed high commitment (Desai & Hogg, 2024).

Economic instability is also a prominent cause of uncertainty in the modern world. Benovska (2024) has shed light on the precarious

situation of Bulgarian Muslims in the contemporary, uncertain world, where they face a threat to their collective identity due to several reasons, like economic uncertainty, also revealing that being repressed in the State leads to individual and collective trauma.

A novel model, Semiotic Dimensionality Model, developed by Salvatore et al. (2023) defines uncertainty to be a lot more than just lack of information. Here, it is regarded as a high mental framework that allows the individual to interpret her/his environment, and when the person fails to do so, it can result in affect-laden meaning-making and experiencing negative emotions, thus overlapping somewhat with Hogg's theory of Uncertainty-Identity, which states that experiencing uncertainty can lead to experiencing negatively valence emotions and thus looking for group membership to strengthen identity. Citing the importance of uncertainty reduction via membership in high-entitativity groups, a study revealed reduced uncertainty-activated arousal in the university students who were a part of groups with high entitativity (Brown et al., 2021).

Despite the excess of literature on various forms of prosocial behaviors, what has yet to be examined carefully is how the individual in need of help (target) might influence whether or not people engage in prosocial behaviors in different situations toward particular ethnic groups. It can be that experiencing pandemic-related economic stress results in helping racial out-group members differently than racial in-group members, partially because of the desire to be close to similar others during times of uncertainty and stress (Carlo et al., 2025).

A study revealed findings contrary to uncertainty-identity theory, in which ethnocentric attitudes were found to be driven less by individual uncertainty avoidance and more by other socio-psychological mechanisms such as socialization, normative cultural beliefs, intergroup threat perceptions, historical narratives, or power and status motivations that operate independently of the need to reduce uncertainty (Černigoj, 2022).

Discussion

The present review has shed light on the existing applications of Uncertainty-Identity Theory over the past two decades and more. As a result, it would be safe to imply that this particular theory has become more pertinent than ever, since uncertainty looms around the world in various facets. Several prominent theories, like Social Identity Theory, Self-Categorization Theory, etc., to which Michael Hogg has contributed enormously, have elucidated the importance of group memberships and their importance in individuals' lives in detail. Being a part of a distinct group provides a sense of stable identity to the members, but uncertainty, being one of the motives to join a group, comes across as a novel and meaningful contribution as one tries to stabilize identity when she/he perceives a threat, and the contemporary world is threatened by financial, professional, personal, and relational means. In the Indian context, the tendency to conform to extremist groups in the face of uncertainty about the future of one's religious orientation can be aptly explained by Uncertainty-Identity Theory. As the norms, rituals, attire, etc. are prototypical of a certain religion and are high in entitativity, the followers tend to identify more with it, as it helps in clearing the uncertain views about oneself and the world at large (Hogg et al., 2010). Apart from identifying with the highly entitative and prototypical group, members rely on the leader of the group and it is the leader who is responsible for maintaining the norms and their

practice by the ingroup members. The more strict the rules, the better the conformity by the group members and hence, the less the ambiguity (Hogg & Adelman, 2013).

Through this thorough review, it was found that the utility of Uncertainty-Identity Theory is not limited to the identification with radical and extreme groups, but also factors like language, economic uncertainty and stress-based arousal can lead to feelings of ambiguity in individuals, which they try to resolve by identifying with relevant groups (Bosman et al., 2024; deBlok & Haugsgjerd, 2025; & Brown et al., 2021). This theory can be extended in the digital dimensions as well as Information and Communication Technologies are reshaping our identities by displaying the content desired by us on social media platforms, and thus becomes easy for an individual to identify with the content present on digital platforms (Floridi, 2014). The effort to identify with the digital content stems from the uncertainty of becoming obsolete in terms of the standards set by the contemporary world. Not knowing the slang in general discourse, not identifying with the influencers, and not having significant knowledge regarding artificial intelligence platforms can force individuals to believe that they can be shunned from society and peer groups anytime in the near future if they do not update their information. They do so by identifying with the groups available in the digital world, which could be in terms of fashion choices, trending artists, viral influencers, etc. Thus, many such activities taking place in the virtual environment could be explained using Uncertainty-Identity Theory.

Future Directions

Uncertainty-Identity Theory can be employed in the literature involving LGBTQ+ participants as the population undergoes identity transitions, be it physical or social, which brings a lot of uncertainty before identifying with a single, most suitable group. The lack of such studies, including this theory, paves the way for fellow researchers to incorporate it as a conceptual framework that can lead to meaningful findings. Migrants also face a lot of ambiguity as they have to sacrifice the most basic rights of shelter and employment while migrating from their homeland to another country or state as they have to deal with inequality-based resource distribution, discrimination on the grounds of ethnicity, and so on. Even though these populations mentioned earlier are vulnerable to uncertainty at every single step of their lives, the literature involving Uncertainty-Identity Theory remains sparse. It would be the appropriate time to investigate the challenges of LGBTQ+ community and migrants as wars are breaking out globally and the movements regarding the sexual orientation and rights of sexually diverse people have gained traction.

Limitations of the Study

The present review on Uncertainty-Identity Theory has included primary studies only and limits the scope to studies in English. Hence, for a broader view of the contributions of this theory, future studies can expand their search to available literature of any kind, including the grey literature as well and studies in other languages could be included.

Conclusion

This review highlights the growing relevance of Uncertainty-Identity Theory (UIT) in the face of global uncertainty, explaining

how individuals join highly entitative, prototypical groups—often with strict norms and authoritarian leaders to deal with identity threats, as seen in Indian religious extremism. UIT extends beyond radicals to linguistic, economic, and stress-induced uncertainties, as well as virtual spaces where algorithms drive trend identification in order to avoid redundancy. Future directions point towards the use of UIT for LGBTQ+ identity transitions, migrants' displacement challenges amid wars and rights movements, and addressing literature gaps through primary research.

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Received February 10, 2026

Revision received March 7, 2026

Accepted March 10, 2026